

ASSESSMENT OF CORE MUSCLE ENDURANCE IN ASYMPTOMATIC COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH POSTERIOR CHAIN TIGHTNESS

Dr. Misbah Banu Khan^{1*}, Dr. Pooja Rathod²

¹Intern (DPO's Nett College of Physiotherapy Thane Mumbai Maharashtra).

²Assistant Professor (DPO's Nett College of Physiotherapy Thane Mumbai Maharashtra).

Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 16 Dec. 2025,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17949336>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Misbah Banu Khan

Intern (DPO's Nett College of
Physiotherapy Thane Mumbai
Maharashtra).

How to cite this Article: Dr. Misbah Banu Khan^{1*}, Dr. Pooja Rathod². (2025). ASSESSMENT OF CORE MUSCLE ENDURANCE IN ASYMPTOMATIC COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH POSTERIOR CHAIN TIGHTNESS. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 400-418. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Background: College students have seen to adapt a flexed posture combining sitting and bending while studying for long hours in a static posture, attending lectures, and commuting to college through public transport on a daily basis. The demanding academic activities in the curriculum of college students which includes physiotherapy students as well make them more susceptible to various musculoskeletal injuries. This may affect the relationship between posterior chain flexibility and core endurance. **Methods:** Total 107 asymptomatic physiotherapy students aged between 19-22 years participated and were screened for posterior chain tightness using the Toe Touch Test, a reliable measure of combined trunk-hip flexion. Core endurance was evaluated using the McGill Core Endurance Test, which assesses anterior, lateral, and posterior trunk musculature through four standardized isometric holds. Flexibility and endurance outcomes were analysed to determine

their potential association. **Results:** The study results showed that participants with posterior chain tightness had reduced core endurance across specific components of the McGill test, suggesting a link between limitations in mobility of posterior chain and reduced ability of core musculature to sustain prolonged static effort. **Conclusion:** The observed clinical findings support the collaborative effort of flexibility and core-strengthening training strategies into preventive health programs within physiotherapy curriculum. This study enables a sense of awareness, precautionary and protective measures that should be taken in

order to minimize the musculoskeletal risks and improve functional performance in physiotherapy students preparing for future professional practise.

KEYWORDS: Posterior muscle chain tightness, Core endurance, Physiotherapy, McGill test, Toe Touch Test.

INTRODUCTION

The muscular chains consist of gravitational muscles that work in synergy to maintain an erect standing posture.^[1]

According to the concept of Anatomy trains, the entire body is linked consisting of superficial back & front line, functional back & front line, spiral line and lateral line myofascial chains proposed by Myers out of which there is good evidence for existence of three chains namely, Superficial back line, Back functional line, Front functional line.^[2]

These myofascial bands for maintaining postural function requires increased endurance muscle fibres in their muscular portions. The posterior chain or superficial backline is responsible for the protection and support of entire posterior surface of the body starting from the bottom of foot till the top of the head, functioning as a continuous line of integrated myofascial.^[3]

Posterior chain muscle of the body consists of thoracic, lumbar and hip extensor muscles, it is a collection of muscles that are interconnected through fascia. Their optimal condition is related and will be dependent on the optimal motor control, strength and endurance.^[4]

The muscles of posterior chain are responsible for maintenance of orthostatic posture against gravitational action making them antigravity muscles.^[5]

Flexibility enhances posture and reduces the incidence of muscle distention and its degree is the amount of painless, smooth movement and without restriction of a joint motion and it's also depended upon the extensibility of the musculotendinous units transposing a joint.^[1,5]

According to available research, the reduced flexibility in adolescence can lead to an increase in the risk of cervical tension in adulthood and a higher prevalence of lumbar hyperlordosis, also is related to knee asymmetry and antero-posterior body inclination. The relation between the physical component flexibility and age is such that it reduces with increasing age.^[7]

According to available research, the reduced flexibility or tightness of the posterior muscles will be associated with conditions like plantar fasciitis and low back pain.^[6,8] The global shortening of posterior chain has been associated with muscular injuries including sports injuries in young individuals.^[9]

The core musculature may be essential in activities of daily living and not only sport performance but also in gaining stability, improving posture, enhancing balance and proprioception. Its components anteriorly include the abdominals, posteriorly the paraspinals and gluteal, superiorly the diaphragm, and inferiorly the pelvic floor and hip girdle musculature.^[10,11]

Core stability might be an important element to improve clinical rehabilitation, health, and physical fitness. Along with this, it also stabilizes peripheral joints and reduces the risk of injury during high levels of physical activity. This consist of components of strength, endurance, flexibility, motor control, and function.^[12]

According to previous studies, decrease in endurance of back extensors in subjects with low back pain. The core muscle endurance refers to the to the ability to sustain a given level of force production over time whereas the strength is maximum torque exerted by the muscle.^[10,11]

College students are exposed to high academic stress during examinations and prolong static posture could be associated with musculoskeletal disorders depending on the reaction to stress.^[13]

Musculoskeletal pain in students leads to discomfort itself, which may limit the student's daily leisure time, increases physical stress and affect study performance students future working capacity and health in their transition to professional life.^[14]

This research has been done to assess core muscle endurance in asymptomatic physiotherapy students with posterior chain tightness.

MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

This was an observational study set in Thane Mumbai Maharashtra India within a duration of 18 months. A total of 107 individuals who were physiotherapy students between the ages 19 to 22 years participated in this study. A written form of consent was taken from all the

participants and the purpose of study along the instructions were explained prior to participation in the study.

Inclusion criteria - Asymptomatic healthy physiotherapy college students, age group of 19 to 22 years, Gender – Male and Female both included, Subjects with posterior chain tightness present.

Exclusion criteria - Subjects with any history of trauma to the back in the past one year or with back pain exceeding one week in the preceding year, spinal conditions or have undergone any spinal surgery, any neurological condition and undergoing any medical treatment for musculoskeletal pain.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethical committee prior to the commencement of the study. The research was conducted at DPO's Nett College of Physiotherapy Thane Mumbai. The demographic data was recorded as per data record sheet.

The participants were first screened for posterior chain tightness with Toe Touch test then those tested positive were assessed for core endurance by McGill test.

The participants stood erect on a foot stool with bare feet placed together, then bend forward as far as possible, while maintaining the knees, arms, and fingers fully extended. The measuring tape was attached on foot stool so as to measure the vertical distance between the tip of the middle finger then reading on the tape was noted, it was positive when the subject did not reach the platform and negative when they could touch the toes or go further beyond. After being screened for posterior chain tightness the participants with reduced flexibility were included in the study and core endurance was assessed.

McGill core endurance test was performed consisting of four endurance tests, with the order randomized among the subjects. Extensor Endurance Test: Subjects were asked to be in prone with the lower body fixed to the test bed at the ankles, knees, and hips and the upper body extended over the edge of the test bench. Subjects rested their upper bodies on the floor before the exertion. At the beginning of the exertion the hands were held across the chest, they were instructed to maintain the horizontal position as long as possible and endurance time was manually recorded in seconds with a stopwatch.

Flexor Endurance Test: subjects were asked to sit on the test bench and place the upper body against a support with an angle of 60° from the test bed. Both the knees and hips were flexed to 90° and the arms were folded across the chest with the hands placed on the opposite shoulder with toes placed under toe straps. Subjects were instructed to maintain the body position while the supporting wedge was pulled back 10cm to begin the test. The test was ended when the upper body fell below the 60° angle.

Side Bridge Test: The subjects had to lay down on an exercise mat on their sides with legs extended performing a side plank along with the top foot was placed in front of the lower foot on the mat for support. Subjects were instructed to support themselves lifting their hips off the mat to maintain a straight line over their full body length, and support themselves on one elbow and their feet. The uninvolved arm was held across the shoulder and same procedure was done on the other side that is both left and right sides were tested.

RESULT

The data collected from 107 individuals was entered using MS Excel 2010 and statistical analysis was done using SPSS23.0v. The qualitative parameters like gender, all the ratio classification presented with frequency and percentages and the quantitative parameters like age and all the ratios presented with the descriptive statistics. To find the association between sex and age with all ratio classifications chi square test was used. P value less than 0.05 considered as significant.

The sample was female-dominant, which is common in physiotherapy programs.

Fig. 1: Sex Distribution across sample size.

The age distribution shows that the majority of participants were between 20 (33.6%) and 22 years (31.8%). The sample is relatively well-distributed, with no single age group dominating excessively, providing a balanced representation of the target population.

Fig. 2: Age Distribution across sample size.

Classification of Core Endurance Ratio Outcomes: The study used the following standard McGill ratios to evaluate balanced core endurance performance: -

1.) Flexor/Extensor Ratio (F/E Ratio): A majority of students demonstrated a poor F/E ratio, indicating that their flexor endurance is disproportionately low compared to extensor endurance. This is clinically relevant because imbalanced flexor–extensor endurance is associated with increased risk of low back pain, spinal instability, and posture-related dysfunction.

Fig. 3: Flexion: Extension Ratio Distribution.

2.) **Right Side Bridge / Left Side Bridge Ratio (RSB/LSB Ratio):** Most students exhibited relatively balanced side-bridge endurance; the majority fell within acceptable ranges.

Fig. 4: Right Side Bridge: Left Side Bridge Ratio Distribution.

3.) **Right Side Bridge / Extensor Ratio (RSB/E Ratio):** There has been an increase in number of students demonstrating a good endurance balance between right-side bridge and extensor muscles compared to those with poor endurance performance.

Fig. 5: Right Side Bridge: Extension Ratio Distribution.

4.) **Left Side Bridge / Extensor Ratio (LSB/E Ratio):** Results are similar to the RSB/E ratio, indicating that nearly two-fifths of students have suboptimal lateral–posterior endurance ratios, potentially predisposing them to unilateral loading patterns.

Fig. 6: Left Side Bridge: Extension Ratio Distribution.

To find the association between sex and age with all ratio classifications we have used chi square test. P value less than 0.05 considered as significant.

Age-Wise Chi-Square Comparisons: - The study examined whether age is associated with core endurance imbalance. Four chi-square tests were conducted.

1. Age × Flexion/Extension Ratio

P-value is 0.045 (significant). Age showed a significant association with F/E ratio classification. Older students (especially aged 22) had a much higher proportion of “Good” ratios compared to younger students. This suggests that as students’ progress through their training years, they may develop relatively better flexor–extensor balance, possibly due to: Exposure to practical training, Increased physical activity, Improved body awareness.

Fig. 7: Age comparisons with Flexion to Extension Ratio.

2. Age × Right Side Bridge/Left Side Bridge Ratio

P-value is 0.114 (not significant). Age doesn't seem to affect lateral side-bridge symmetry. In other words, balance here doesn't really change as students get older.

Fig. 8: Age comparisons with Right Side Bridge to Left Side Bridge Ratio

3. Age × Right Side Bridge/Extension Ratio.

P-value is 0.868 (not significant). Also not significant. Right-side bridge to extensor endurance stays pretty much the same, no matter the age group. Endurance distribution across these muscle groups remains consistent across age groups.

Fig. 9: Age comparisons with Right Side Bridge to Extension Ratio.

4. Age × Left Side Bridge/Extension Ratio

P-value is 0.57 (not significant). There is no association between age and left-side bridge to extensor ratios, confirming that lateral endurance patterns are stable, regardless of age.

Fig. 10: Age comparisons with Left Side Bridge to Extension Ratio.

Sex-Wise Chi-Square Comparisons

5. Sex × Flexion/Extension Ratio

P-value is 0.845 (not significant) Both males and females showed similar patterns of good vs. poor F/E ratios. This means that sex does not influence flexor–extensor balance in this sample.

Fig. 11: Sex comparisons with Flexion to Extension Ratio.

6. Sex × Right Side Bridge/Left Side Bridge Ratio

P-value is 0.067 (not significant but close to significance). Males had fewer “poor” ratios, hinting at possibly better lateral symmetry, but the evidence is insufficient.

Fig. 12: Sex comparisons with Right Side Bridge to Left Side Bridge Ratio.

7. Sex × Right Side Bridge/Extension Ratio

P-value is 0.399 (not significant). Endurance balance between right-side bridge and extensors looks the same for both sexes.

Fig.13: Sex comparisons with Right Side Bridge to Extension Ratio.

8. Sex × Left Side Bridge/Extension Ratio

P-value is 0.923 (not significant). Likewise, sex has no significant effect on left-side bridge to extensor ratio. Both groups display similar endurance patterns.

Fig.14: Sex comparisons with Left Side Bridge to Extension Ratio.

Chi-Square Test Results

Significant Association

F/E Ratio by Age: $\chi^2 p = 0.045$ (statistically significant)

Age 22 had the highest proportion of “Good” F/E ratios (20.6%), while age 21 had none. The effect size was small (Cramér’s $V \approx 0.159$).

No significant associations were found for the other ratios by age or sex.

Performance by Age: Analysis showed a general decline in flexor and extensor durations with advancing age within the studied range, although the difference was not always statistically significant or linear.

Performance by Gender: Both males and females predominantly showed poor FE Ratios, but ratios such as RSLSB, RSBE, and LSBE were not significantly different between sexes, further confirming posterior chain tightness as the main factor affecting endurance rather than gender.

Descriptive Statistics for Core Endurance Tests

These are detailed descriptive statistics for: Trunk Flexor endurance, Trunk Extensor endurance, Right Side Bridge & Left Side Bridge

Across all age groups: Endurance times were below McGill’s normative values, indicating overall weakness or deconditioning among students.

Standard deviations were high, showing large inter-individual variability.

Age had modest effects: older participants (22 years) showed slightly lower performance in most metrics, potentially due to lifestyle factors or academic strain.

Table 1: Statistics.

		Age (Years)	Trunk Flexors Test (Sec)	Trunk Extensor Test (Sec)	Right Side Bridge (Sec)	Left Side bridge (Sec)	F/E Ratio	RSB/LSB Ratio	RSB/E Ratio	LSB/E Ratio
N	Valid	107	107	107	107	107	107	107	107	107
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		20.68	42.21	23.67	14.66	15.47	2.3596	.9596	.7867	.8230
Median		21.00	39.00	20.00	13.00	13.00	2.1500	.8600	.6100	.6700
Std. Deviation		1.078	17.302	16.405	8.609	8.109	1.32739	.28298	.53525	.48106
Minimum		19	13	4	2	2	.29	.44	.17	.14
Maximum		22	98	82	44	38	7.00	1.67	2.63	2.25
Percentiles	25	20.00	28.00	12.00	8.00	10.00	1.5500	.7500	.4000	.5000
	50	21.00	39.00	20.00	13.00	13.00	2.1500	.8600	.6100	.6700
	75	22.00	53.00	31.00	19.00	21.00	2.9200	1.1800	1.1300	1.2000

Table 2: Descriptives.

Age (Years)	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound			
Trunk Flexors Test (Sec)	19	16	48.19	17.069	4.267	39.09	57.28	26	75
	20	36	42.44	15.689	2.615	37.14	47.75	22	98
	21	21	46.10	15.000	3.273	39.27	52.92	25	83
	22	34	36.74	19.336	3.316	29.99	43.48	13	90
	Total	107	42.21	17.302	1.673	38.89	45.52	13	98
Trunk Extensor Test (Sec)	19	16	25.88	13.928	3.482	18.45	33.30	7	51
	20	36	21.36	12.438	2.073	17.15	25.57	5	58
	21	21	22.76	14.649	3.197	16.09	29.43	4	64
	22	34	25.65	21.667	3.716	18.09	33.21	4	82
	Total	107	23.67	16.405	1.586	20.53	26.82	4	82
Right Side Bridge (Sec)	19	16	15.50	8.075	2.019	11.20	19.80	6	33
	20	36	16.83	10.044	1.674	13.43	20.23	3	44

	21	21	15.10	8.372	1.827	11.28	18.91	4	34
	22	34	11.71	6.658	1.142	9.38	14.03	2	29
	Total	107	14.66	8.609	.832	13.01	16.31	2	44
Left Side bridge (Sec)	19	16	15.31	7.355	1.839	11.39	19.23	6	33
	20	36	16.72	8.228	1.371	13.94	19.51	5	36
	21	21	17.00	9.306	2.031	12.76	21.24	6	38
	22	34	13.26	7.358	1.262	10.70	15.83	2	32
	Total	107	15.47	8.109	.784	13.91	17.02	2	38
F/E Ratio	19	16	2.2525	.94285	.23571	1.7501	2.7549	.78	3.73
	20	36	2.3897	1.13816	.18969	2.0046	2.7748	.91	6.13
	21	21	2.6462	1.58297	.34543	1.9256	3.3667	1.18	7.00
	22	34	2.2012	1.50941	.25886	1.6745	2.7278	.29	7.00
	Total	107	2.3596	1.32739	.12832	2.1052	2.6140	.29	7.00
RSB/LSB Ratio	19	16	1.0181	.23746	.05937	.8916	1.1447	.67	1.33
	20	36	.9981	.29456	.04909	.8984	1.0977	.60	1.67
	21	21	.9038	.23980	.05233	.7947	1.0130	.55	1.67
	22	34	.9259	.31350	.05376	.8165	1.0353	.44	1.50
	Total	107	.9596	.28298	.02736	.9054	1.0139	.44	1.67
RSB/E Ratio	19	16	.7400	.46184	.11546	.4939	.9861	.21	1.74
	20	36	.8903	.50425	.08404	.7197	1.0609	.21	2.00
	21	21	.8800	.68440	.14935	.5685	1.1915	.20	2.63
	22	34	.6415	.47926	.08219	.4742	.8087	.17	2.25
	Total	107	.7867	.53525	.05174	.6841	.8893	.17	2.63
LSB/E Ratio	19	16	.7569	.47546	.11887	.5035	1.0102	.26	1.71
	20	36	.9108	.48588	.08098	.7464	1.0752	.33	2.00
	21	21	.9257	.56032	.12227	.6707	1.1808	.30	2.25
	22	34	.6976	.40801	.06997	.5553	.8400	.14	1.50
	Total	107	.8230	.48106	.04651	.7308	.9152	.14	2.25

Table 3: Group Statistics.

Sex		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Trunk Flexors Test (Sec)	Male	19	43.42	16.704	3.832
	Female	88	41.94	17.511	1.867
Trunk Extensor Test (Sec)	Male	19	26.84	16.341	3.749
	Female	88	22.99	16.431	1.752
Right Side Bridge (Sec)	Male	19	16.79	9.426	2.162
	Female	88	14.20	8.409	.896
Left Side bridge (Sec)	Male	19	15.95	6.536	1.499
	Female	88	15.36	8.439	.900
F/E Ratio	Male	19	2.1742	1.38183	.31701
	Female	88	2.3997	1.32007	.14072
RSB/LSB Ratio	Male	19	1.0084	.21567	.04948
	Female	88	.9491	.29548	.03150
RSB/E Ratio	Male	19	.8126	.62837	.14416
	Female	88	.7811	.51690	.05510
LSB/E Ratio	Male	19	.8247	.56217	.12897
	Female	88	.8226	.46537	.04961

Overall Clinical Interpretation

Core Muscle Imbalance: This study demonstrates a high prevalence of poor F/E ratios among students with posterior chain tightness, suggesting a strong association between posterior flexibility deficits and core endurance dysfunction. The elevated mean F/E ratio (2.36) indicates that trunk flexors are disproportionately stronger/more enduring than extensors.

Age-Related Variations: The significant association between age and F/E ratio performance suggests that even within this narrow age range (19-22 years), there are meaningful differences in core muscle balance development.

Lateral Balance Preservation: Despite poor flexor-extensor balance, approximate rise in number of participants maintaining good lateral core balance (RSB/LSB ratios), indicating that posterior chain tightness may specifically affect anterior-posterior core balance rather than lateral stability.

DISCUSSION

This research aims to assess core muscle endurance in asymptomatic physiotherapy students with posterior chain tightness. The study is motivated by the high prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders among college students, particularly those in physiotherapy programs, due to prolonged static postures and academic stress. This research methodology

involves screening participants for posterior chain tightness using the Toe Touch Test, followed by core endurance assessment using the McGill Core Endurance Test, which allows for a comprehensive evaluation of both flexibility and endurance—two components central to musculoskeletal function.

The posterior chain—often described within myofascial models—plays a central role in stabilizing posture and supporting the body against gravitational load. Thomas Myers' framework highlights how these structures operate as interconnected chains rather than as isolated muscles, providing a systems-based view of human movement.

Reduced flexibility in this chain has been associated with various conditions, including plantar fasciitis and low back pain. Marcia Regina da Silva and colleagues (2017) reported that low back pain was common among rural laborers, and that limited flexibility was associated with more pronounced functional difficulties. This relationship was notably stronger in female participants.

Similarly, according to Lopes *et al.* (2021), individuals who exhibit weaker trunk endurance or reduced flexibility in the posterior chain appear more likely to experience subsequent injuries of the lower back or lower limbs, particularly when they also have a prior history of musculoskeletal discomfort.

The Toe Touch Test was used to assess posterior chain flexibility. Kippers and Parker (1987) noted that the Toe Touch Test provides a dependable estimate of combined hip and trunk flexion. Subsequent research has reported excellent consistency of the test in both healthy groups and in people with low back pain, with reliability coefficients approaching the upper range of accepted clinical standards.

Core muscle endurance is essential for stability, posture, and injury prevention. The McGill Core Endurance Test, which evaluates the endurance capacity of major trunk stabilizers, is widely regarded as a dependable clinical assessment. It uses four standardized isometric positions to quantify how long individuals can maintain controlled postures. McGill and colleagues (1999) also proposed normative endurance ratios that help clinicians interpret whether a person's trunk musculature is functioning in a balanced manner.

Findings from Abdelraouf *et al.* (2016) indicate that individuals with reduced core endurance tend to report more frequent episodes of nonspecific low back pain. Their results support the

idea that reduced endurance in the trunk musculature may contribute to the development or persistence of these symptoms.

This research is particularly relevant given the findings of Ekpenyong *et al.* (2013), who observed that university students who experienced greater academic pressure were also more likely to report musculoskeletal complaints which in turn suggests that, the ways students respond to and manage stress may influence their susceptibility to these disorders.

The data in this study suggest posterior chain tightness detrimentally affects the ability to maintain core endurance in students, particularly in the flexor-extensor ratio, potentially predisposing these students to future musculoskeletal disorders. By focusing on physiotherapy students, this study adds vital data to a growing body of literature suggesting that sedentary lifestyles and academic demands heighten the risk for muscle tightness and diminished core endurance. Overall, the findings highlight the need for proactive programs that improve flexibility and core stability, which can help prevent injuries and foster better musculoskeletal health in students.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study addresses an important gap in the literature by examining the relationship between posterior chain tightness and core muscle endurance in asymptomatic physiotherapy students.

The findings state that asymptomatic collegiate physiotherapy students with posterior chain tightness have markedly reduced core muscle endurance, as validated by both McGill tests and ratio analyse, which in turn suggest that physiotherapy students may be at increased risk for: Low back strain, Poor trunk stabilization, Postural dysfunction, Reduced functional capacity for clinical tasks.

The core muscular imbalance observed may predispose them to musculoskeletal injuries during their education and future professional activities. Preventative physiotherapy programs in the curriculum focusing on posterior chain flexibility and core endurance are recommended.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would express my sincere gratitude to those people without whose support and concern this project would not have been possible. I would like to acknowledge and thank all the participants who willingly participated in this study.

REFERENCES

1. Francisco J. González-Álvarez et al. Effects of diaphragm stretching on posterior chain muscle kinematics and rib cage and abdominal excursion: a randomized controlled trial. *Braz J Phys Ther.*, Sep-Oct. 2016; 20(5): 405–411.
2. Jan Wilke, MA et al. What Is Evidence-Based About Myofascial Chains: A Systematic Review *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 2016; 97: 454-61.
3. Thomas WM. *Anatomy train myofascial meridians for manual and movement therapist's* 2nd edition Churchill Livingstone, 2009.
4. Eline MD De Ridder et al. Posterior muscle chain activity during various extension exercises: an observational study Published online, Jul. 9, 2013. doi: 10.1186/1471-2474-14-204.
5. Israel de Lucena Marques et al. Effect of the Muscle Energy Technique and Self-Stretching on Flexibility Gain of Posterior Chain. *International Archives of Medicine Section: Exercise & Psychosomatic Medicine*, 2016.
6. Marcia Regina da Silva et. al. Posterior chain flexibility and lower back pain in farm workers. *Fisioter.mov.*, Curitiba, apr/June 2017; 30(2): 219-226.
7. Effect of Pilates Matwork exercises on posterior chain flexibility and trunk mobility in school children: A randomized clinical trial.
8. Yolanda Aranda Bolívar Relationship Between Tightness of the Posterior Muscles of the Lower Limb and Plantar Fasciitis. published online, January 1, 2013.
9. Sabrina almeida porto et al. Flexibility of posterior muscle chain in amateur soccer athletes, 2019; 6(5). (*IJAERS*).
10. Sarah L. Strand,1 John Hjelm, Todd C. Shoepe, Norms for an Isometric Muscle Endurance Test. *J Hum Kinet*, Mar. 27, 2014; 40: 93–102.
11. Osama Ragaa Abdelraouf et al. The relationship b/w core endurance & back dysfunction in collegiate male athletes with and without non-specific low back pain, Jun. 2016; 11(3): 337–344.

12. Stuart M. McGill et al. Endurance Times for Low Back Stabilization Exercises: Clinical Targets for Testing and Training From a Normal Database. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 1999; 80: 941-4.
13. Christopher E. Ekpenyong et al. *Ethiop J Health Sci.*, July 2013; 23(2). Original Article Associations Between Academic Stressors, Reaction to Stress, Coping Strategies and Musculoskeletal Disorders Among College Students. *Ethiop J Health Sci.*, July 2013; 23: 2.
14. Saumya P. Prajapati et al. Prevalence of Musculoskeletal Disorder among College Students in Times of COVID-19 Pandemic - An Observational Study. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research*, October 2021; 11(10).